

Diaspora Engagement in Transition Assistance: Bolstering Local Resources and Agency

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Acknowledgments

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This **IFIT Policy Brief** explores the importance of integrating diaspora engagement into “transition assistance”: a term used to refer to the assistance offered to countries in transition out of war or autocracy. It outlines key lessons and guidance on emerging opportunities to strengthen the resources and agency of countries before and during their transitions.

Introduction

Transition assistance is undergoing a period of transformation. Countries and communities are struggling to secure the resources and technical support needed to build and sustain meaningful and lasting transitions. However, while the challenges facing countries can vary tremendously, a common thread across many of these contexts is the marginalisation of indigenous and diaspora financial and non-financial capital and influence. Without greater emphasis on this, countries are less able to lead, shape, and deliver successful transitions. Yet, current aid paradigms rarely reinforce these elements.

Diaspora engagement can change this equation. Diasporas represent a growing global phenomenon. In 1990, about 150 million people lived outside the country of their birth; today, that number has nearly doubled to 304 million, excluding second- and third-generation diaspora, which significantly raises the figure. This unprecedented scale and distribution of global migration underscore the urgent need, and opportunity, to better leverage diaspora potential in transition settings.

Encouragingly, several countries are beginning to demonstrate what forward-thinking, institutionalised diaspora engagement can look like in practice. Ukraine, for example, has made diaspora integration a formal part of its national recovery and reconstruction agenda by appointing an Ambassador-at-Large for the global diaspora,¹ establishing a Ministry of National Unity,² and launching the Create Ukraine programme to attract diaspora talent into reform and public service.³ Similarly, in post-dictatorship Gambia, the government adopted a comprehensive diaspora strategy in 2018 as part of its new National Development Plan (NDP), formally recognised the diaspora as the Eighth Region of The Gambia, created a dedicated Diaspora and Migration Directorate, and appointed professionals as Honorary Consuls and Ambassadors-at-Large worldwide.⁴ These efforts reflect a broader recognition that diaspora capital is not supplemental, but foundational to building inclusive and resilient transitions.

This paper argues that a more deliberate and strategic incorporation of diaspora engagement – through diplomacy, philanthropy, knowledge transfer, investment, and partnerships – is critical to addressing core gaps in agency, relevance, and resourcing both for countries directly in transition and for the broader evolution of transition assistance itself. Against this backdrop, this policy brief 1) outlines the case for diaspora engagement in transition assistance; 2) explores a framework for understanding diaspora capital across four dimensions – economic, human, social, and cultural; 3) examines key challenges limiting effective diaspora engagement; and 4) presents policy implications and practical entry points to embed diaspora capital as a core element of transition strategies.

While this paper uses the term “diaspora” in an inclusive sense, it may not reflect the lived identity of all transnational communities. In particular, refugees, exiles, and stateless persons may not identify with the term due to its associations with voluntary migration or privilege. Nonetheless, their experiences and contributions are understood as both distinctive and complementary.

Why Diaspora Engagement Matters for Transition Assistance

As a field, transition assistance has long championed the principle of local ownership. Yet in practice, most transitions remain externally driven and insufficiently resourced. This gap has only widened as geopolitical realignments, economic uncertainty, and protracted crises make traditional aid models less predictable and less effective.

In this context, diaspora engagement presents a compelling and underutilised opportunity. Diaspora communities, defined as individuals and groups with ancestral or affinity-based ties to a place other than where they currently live, are uniquely positioned to contribute to inclusive transitions.⁵ Often shaped by displacement, migration, or transnational identity, diasporas represent both a continuity of local experience and a gateway to global networks. Their potential lies in their hybrid identity: they are both insiders and outsiders, able to act as cultural translators, bridge-builders, and drivers of innovation.

Diaspora engagement speaks directly to three deficits that often undermine transition assistance:

- **Agency**, by reinforcing the leadership and legitimacy of actors with lived experience and long-term commitment to their country of origin.
- **Relevance**, by ensuring that policy and assistance strategies reflect the complexity of identity, need, and aspiration among affected communities.
- **Resourcing**, by tapping into financial and non-financial capital that is often more flexible, sustained, and trust-based than traditional aid.

In 2024, remittance flows to low- and middle-income countries were projected to reach US\$685 billion – surpassing both foreign direct investment (FDI) and official development assistance (ODA) combined.⁶ Countries identified in the Organisation for Economic Co-operation and Development (OECD) fragility index alone received US\$148.1 billion in remittances in 2023, compared to just US\$92 billion in ODA and US\$37.8 billion in FDI.⁷

Yet, remittances represent only one part of “diaspora capital”, which is best understood across four interconnected dimensions:

- **Economic**, including remittances, savings, direct investments, and market linkages;
- **Human**, including technical expertise, professional networks, and lived experience;
- **Social**, including trust-based relationships, civic engagement, and advocacy capacity; and
- **Cultural**, including shared values, identity narratives, and influence across generations.

As outlined in more detail below, these different forms of capital highlight the enormous potential of the diaspora to enhance transition assistance.

A Longstanding but Evolving Role

Diasporas are not new actors in transitions. Historically, they have played central roles, whether as peacebuilders or, in some cases, spoilers. Over the past two decades, international organisations have begun to examine these roles more systematically, especially within the so-called humanitarian-development-peace (HDP) nexus. For example, initiatives like DEMAC (Diaspora Emergency Action & Coordination) have advanced this agenda by documenting diaspora responses to crises in Syria, Somalia, South Sudan, and Ukraine.⁸

Particularly in fragile and conflict-affected settings, diaspora actors often fill critical gaps in state capacity. Their networks can deliver aid, build social cohesion, mobilise political pressure, or accelerate post-conflict recovery, sometimes in ways that governments or donors cannot. One of the clearest examples of this is the role of the Irish diaspora in the Northern Ireland peace process. In the United States, diaspora leaders played a vital role in advancing peace by mobilising strategic interventions across diplomacy, media, philanthropy, and politics. Their advocacy helped secure the Clinton Administration's role as a peace broker. Additionally, platforms like *The Ireland Funds* have, to date, raised over US\$650 million for peace, culture, education, and community development across the island of Ireland.⁹ In one standout initiative, diaspora leaders organised and funded a delegation of Northern Irish community leaders to meet Nelson Mandela in South Africa, an encounter many cited as a turning point ahead of the Good Friday Agreement.¹⁰ This case exemplifies how diaspora capital can transcend bureaucratic limits and catalyse high-impact political change.

Understanding the Opportunity

To appreciate how diaspora actors can play a central role in building more resilient and inclusive transitions, this section expands on the four different types of diaspora capital and how each can serve as a structural entry point for improved transition assistance.

1. **Diaspora Economic Capital:** This encompasses financial resources mobilised by diaspora communities. While remittances are often the most visible form, economic capital also encompasses direct investments made by diaspora members in business activities, such as small and medium-sized enterprises, real estate, and innovation hubs. It also refers to any economic resource used to buy or make products and provide services that contribute to job creation, livelihoods, or the provision of essential services in transition contexts. Economic capital can be channelled through formal mechanisms, such as diaspora bonds or pooled investment funds, or through informal, community-based initiatives.¹¹

Entry Points for Transition Assistance: Diaspora economic capital serves as a gateway to agency and power for localised transition assistance as diasporas represent local communities with a global impact.

- In economic terms, diaspora actors support capacity for delivery, flexible financing, and innovative experimentation.

- At a political level, the financial engagement of diasporas can drive accountability, enhance institutional strength, and expand decision-making agency for local actors.
- The economic capital of diasporas can contribute to security by enhancing financial and scientific capacity, as well as traditional peacebuilding, as seen in Northern Ireland.
- Societally, the economic capital of diasporas can empower communities through increased localisation, equity, and improved livelihoods.

In environmental domains, diasporas can help build infrastructure for resilience and technological change. They have been referred to as “the invisible heroes of climate action”.¹²

Nigeria: Diaspora Bonds as a Tool for Inclusive Financing and Reform

In 2017, Nigeria issued a diaspora bond aimed at retail investors abroad, successfully raising US\$300 million from Nigerians living in the United States, the United Kingdom, and other countries.¹³ Registered with both the U.S. Securities and Exchange Commission and the UK Listing Authority, the five-year bond offered a 5.625% annual return and was oversubscribed by approximately 130%, indicating strong confidence among the diaspora.¹⁴ The initiative was part of a broader effort by the Nigerian government to diversify funding sources for infrastructure development, while also formalising diaspora engagement through institutions such as the Nigerians in Diaspora Commission (NiDCOM).

By creating an accessible, government-backed investment mechanism, the bond transformed diaspora members from only senders of remittances into long-term development investors. It also demonstrated the potential for national institutions to unlock diaspora capital at scale through transparent and regulated financial instruments.

Impact

Nigeria’s diaspora bond marked a notable shift in the country’s approach to engaging diaspora financial capital, setting a precedent for regulated, retail-oriented instruments. While the US\$300 million raised was modest in comparison to the US\$25 billion in annual remittances, the bond’s oversubscription suggested a degree of diaspora willingness to invest in formal government-backed channels.¹⁵ Nevertheless, public opinion on the bond’s impact remains mixed. While some viewed it as a step toward institutionalising diaspora investment, others criticised it as deepening public debt without sufficient transparency or accountability regarding how the funds were ultimately used. These concerns highlight the importance of embedding diaspora financing tools within broader frameworks of trust, governance, and fiscal responsibility. Even so, Nigeria’s experience remains a reference point for countries exploring new avenues to leverage diaspora capital in transition or development contexts.

2. **Diaspora Human Capital:** This refers to the skills, knowledge, and experience possessed by an individual or population in the diaspora, and which can be mobilised to support reform, service delivery, and institution-building in their countries of origin.¹⁶ It includes sectoral expertise (e.g., in health, education, governance, or technology) as well as leadership and innovation capacities gained abroad. Diaspora human capital can be transferred through temporary or virtual return programmes, technical assistance, training, or mentorship initiatives, and is especially valuable in contexts where domestic capacity in the country of origin is weak or recovering.

Entry Points for Transition Assistance: Diaspora human capital enables reimagined partnerships and involves exchanging ideas and innovations that transcend geography. Such capital can facilitate:

- Market intelligence and integration through "ideas, behaviours, identities, and social capital that flow from receiving to sending communities".¹⁷
- Political access and network development to strengthen institutional quality.
- Enhanced competitiveness, reputational resilience, and scientific capabilities.
- Deeper integration with local talent to improve inclusion, productivity, and long-term developmental outcomes such as education and self-confidence.
- Sharing scientific and technological knowledge to address environmental challenges.

Lebanon: Knowledge Sharing for Social Benefit

With at least 10 million Lebanese living abroad, the diaspora is much larger than Lebanon's current population of 5.7 million.¹⁸ The economic impact of the diaspora is significant. In 2023, remittances accounted for 38% of Lebanon's GDP.¹⁹ This has been critical as the country has faced prolonged crises and has dropped in status from upper-middle income to lower-middle income according to the World Bank classifications.²⁰

Impact

In 2017, Lebanon expanded political participation by granting diaspora voting rights and allocating six parliamentary seats to emigrants, prompting over 82,000 registrations across 40 countries. Alongside this, the "transfer of knowledge through expatriate nationals" (TOKTEN) programme led to the training of 600 Lebanese nationals and supported 16 organisations in its final years.²¹ Meanwhile, the Lebanese International Finance Executives (LIFE) programme raised US\$16.5 million for scholarships, US\$9.4 million for humanitarian aid, and helped create over 1,100 jobs.²² These initiatives highlight how structured diaspora engagement can channel expertise, networks, and opportunities in fragile and transition contexts.

3. **Diaspora Social Capital:** This refers to the networks of relationships that enable diaspora communities to mobilise support, influence policy, and link local actors with international institutions, donors, or policy platforms. In transition settings,

diaspora social capital can manifest itself in many ways, such as through civic participation, political advocacy, coalition-building, and partnerships with reform actors. Diaspora social capital also includes the ability to bridge communal divides and foster social cohesion, making it a powerful enabler of both legitimacy and resilience.

Entry Points for Transition Assistance: Diaspora social capital provides a relational edge to ensure that transition assistance is more inclusive. It can contribute by:

- Enhancing business efficiency and facilitating market integration.
- Building political access and strengthening diplomacy.
- Providing reputational security to strengthen both information systems and civic legitimacy*.
- Expanding transparency between stakeholders and contributing to behavioural change and improved health outcomes.
- Advocating environmental issues while ensuring local buy-in and knowledge transfer.

The Gambia: Diaspora Technical Cooperation for National Dialogue and Civic Infrastructure

In 2017, following the end of 22 years of authoritarian rule, the Migration and Sustainable Development in The Gambia (MSDG) project was launched as a diaspora-led Technical Assistance and Technical Cooperation Programme.²³ Spearheaded by diaspora-led GKPartners in collaboration with the governments of The Gambia and Switzerland, MSDG stands out as one of the few diaspora-led cooperation programmes globally.²⁴

A core feature of MSDG was its mobilisation of diaspora social capital to build sustained partnerships between diaspora professionals and national institutions. The project facilitated long-term collaboration with over 20 government ministries, departments, and agencies, and convened eight sectoral networks.²⁵ Among its key contributions, MSDG supported the development of the National Assembly Television (NATV) infrastructure, providing full coverage of parliamentary proceedings and making them accessible to all media platforms.²⁶ It also institutionalised the annual Stake in the Nation Forum (SNF), chaired by the President and attended by diaspora representatives, civil society, and government actors to promote inclusive policy dialogue.²⁷

Impact

Between 2017 and 2024, MSDG implemented approximately 200 diaspora-led interventions across all regions of the country.²⁸ It embedded civic transparency mechanisms, generated cross-sectoral partnerships, and strengthened trust between diaspora communities and public institutions. The Gambia's experience underscores the importance of structured diaspora social capital in supporting national dialogue, promoting inclusive governance, and reinforcing democratic legitimacy in fragile and transition settings.

* For more information on reputational security, please see: Nicholas J. Cull, *Reputational Security: Refocusing Public Diplomacy for a Dangerous World* (Cambridge: Polity Press, 2023).

4. **Diaspora Cultural Capital:** This refers to the “acquisition and transfer of new values, perspectives, and ideas by diaspora communities that enrich the diversity and resilience of societies”.²⁹ Through media, arts, education, and public discourse, diasporas can promote inclusive national identity, challenge divisive narratives, and foster a culture of dialogue and pluralism. In transitions where issues of identity, legitimacy, and social cohesion are central, diaspora cultural capital can play a significant role in shaping public understanding and advancing reconciliation.

Entry Points for Transition Assistance: Diaspora cultural capital empowers both community-led and network-driven agency. It can enhance:

- De-risking and market readiness for economic engagement.
- Political reform processes, governance values, and foreign policy visibility.
- Social cohesion, inclusion, and stakeholder transparency.
- Human development indicators, including gender equity, health, and talent acquisition.
- Environmentally responsive innovation, both local and imported.

Zimbabwe: The Zimbabwe Diaspora Nation Building Initiative

In response to Zimbabwe’s prolonged political and economic challenges, the Zimbabwe Diaspora Nation Building Initiative (ZDNBI) was established in 2020 as a formal platform to engage Zimbabweans abroad in national recovery.³⁰ Operating through regional Apex Associations in the UK, South Africa, Canada, and Australia, ZDNBI combined cultural, policy, and investment efforts with the aim to reinforce national cohesion.³¹

Working in partnership with the International Organization for Migration (IOM), the national government and civil society, ZDNBI played a central role in the design and public consultation process for the development of the National Diaspora Policy.³² The policy, adopted in 2016 and updated with ZDNBI’s support in 2021, formally recognised the diaspora as a key stakeholder in national development and transitional reform processes.³³

Impact

ZDNBI’s diaspora policy consultations contributed to legal reforms on dual citizenship and diaspora voting, and formalised pathways for returnees in key sectors.³⁴ Between 2020 and 2022, ZDNBI convened homecoming events and investment forums, engaging many diaspora participants. These gatherings led to the signing of project agreements with local SMEs and support for heritage initiatives, reinforcing the diaspora’s role in deepening Zimbabwe’s cultural capital and civic dialogue spaces.³⁵

Addressing Consistent Challenges

Despite increasing recognition of its potential value, diaspora engagement remains underdeveloped and under-resourced. This is likely because formalised diaspora engagement, by both state and non-state actors, is relatively nascent. But if four recurring challenges can be surmounted, there is a significant opportunity to reimagine the work of diaspora engagement and substantially expand and enhance diaspora contributions.

1. Limited Policy Infrastructure

A mapping of more than 110 countries by the EU Global Diaspora Facility (EUDiF) found that 80 have at least one institution dedicated to diaspora engagement, but only 25% have adopted a formal diaspora engagement policy.³⁶ In total, EUDiF identified over 430 public or semi-public institutions in these countries, operating across eight key sectors including economic development and skills transfer, culture and education, liaison and networking, labour migration, policy and legal frameworks, and return and reintegration.³⁷

However, in general, diaspora engagement is ad hoc rather than strategic. The absence of coherent frameworks undermines coordination, hinders resource mobilisation, and limits long-term impact, particularly in fragile and transition settings. The Diaspora Institute notes as the “fireworks syndrome”: enthusiastic bursts of engagement that quickly fade due to weak systems and limited follow-through.³⁸

2. Trust Deficits

Some diaspora communities are shaped by experiences of displacement, marginalisation, or political exclusion from their countries of origin, resulting in scepticism toward state-led efforts. The distrust cuts across all forms of diaspora capital: financial contributions may be withheld due to concerns about mismanagement or corruption; skills and expertise may go untapped when engagement feels politicised; and outreach may wane when there are doubts about meaningful inclusion. However, distrust does not deter diasporas from wanting to contribute. Instead, it means that countries in transition must develop an agile architecture of diaspora engagement where the state plays different roles – as enablers, convenors, and guarantors – rather than being the sole drivers. Rebuilding trust requires more than outreach; it demands consistent co-creation, transparency, and the involvement of credible intermediaries who are seen as legitimate across both diaspora and domestic spheres.

3. Fragmented Ecosystems

In many transition settings, diaspora engagement lacks coordination and continuity. Multiple institutions may pursue engagement independently, leading to duplication, confusion, and inconsistent follow-through. In addition, short-term projects dominate while long-term strategies remain underdeveloped. Together, this limits the ability to mobilise diaspora economic capital, channel technical expertise, or build inclusive, trust-based networks. To move beyond symbolic or isolated efforts, countries must invest in diaspora ecosystem-building – creating structured platforms that enable sustained dialogue, align engagement with national priorities, and demonstrate what countries and communities in transition can offer the diaspora.

4. Overemphasis on Financial Inputs

A persistent challenge of diaspora engagement is the tendency to focus primarily on remittances. While significant, this narrow framing reduces diaspora actors to donors and overlooks their broader roles – as “brain gainers, altruistic technologists, brave capital investors, catalysts, and diplomats”.³⁹ When engagement strategies ignore human, social, and cultural capital, they miss critical opportunities for co-creation and long-term partnership. A more holistic approach is needed – one that recognises the diversity of diaspora identities and aligns strategies with their motivations, capacities, and senses of belonging.

Unlocking Diaspora Impact: Policy Implications and Priorities

Realising the full potential of diaspora engagement in transition assistance requires moving beyond short-term initiatives and fragmented efforts toward long-term strategies that embed diaspora capital – economic, human, social, and cultural – as a core pillar of national transition agendas. Likewise, diasporas can do more to step into the limelight of leadership and ownership.

Looking ahead, the following priorities can serve as a foundation for more impactful, inclusive, and resilient diaspora involvement in fragile and transition contexts:

- 1. Engage Diasporas from the Start:** Diaspora actors should be involved from the design phase of transition assistance through to implementation and grounded in dialogue about what the diaspora is willing and prepared to contribute. Successful examples from India, Jamaica, and Ireland demonstrate the general importance of sustained platforms for consultation and co-creation. India’s Pravasi Bharatiya Divas, a large-scale annual forum, has become a cornerstone for celebrating diaspora contributions and shaping policy initiatives, such as the Pravasi Kaushal Vikas Yojana, which equips emigrant workers with skills for employment abroad.⁴⁰ Jamaica’s JA Diaspora Engage, a digital platform, facilitates real-time two-way interaction between diaspora communities and public institutions, offering services ranging from labour market access to data-sharing with ministries.⁴¹ Ireland’s Global Irish Civic Forum brings together diaspora civil society leaders to co-develop initiatives and influence national diaspora strategy.⁴²
- 2. Embrace Shared Leadership:** Diaspora engagement thrives when responsibility is shared between state and non-state actors. When diasporas feel a genuine sense of belonging – defined not just by identity but by connection to place, power, and purpose – their engagement becomes more sustained and transformative.⁴³ At its best, this includes cultivating a new generation of leaders, across government, civil society, and diaspora networks, skilled in co-creation, network building, and cross-cultural diplomacy.
- 3. Embed the “Three I’s” of Institutions, Information, and Implementation:** Effective diaspora engagement calls for three interlocking pillars. First, embedding diaspora engagement within broader national plans and institutional frameworks helps to build momentum and accountability. Second, strong diaspora engagement strategies include tools for diaspora data that prospect capacities, preferences, and

evolving roles for the diaspora. Ongoing research and development (R&D) efforts can help ensure policies remain relevant and responsive to the dynamics of diaspora communities. Third, successful diaspora engagement requires a long-term national investment that is harmonised across actors and regularly evaluated.

4. **Leverage Strategic Entry Points:** To translate commitment into results, countries should focus on avenues of engagement that match diaspora motivations with national priorities:
 - *Diaspora diplomacy:* Diaspora actors can serve as credible intermediaries and advocates on the global stage. In fragile contexts, they often help mobilise support or foster new alliances. Their transnational reach, emotional ties, and community-rooted legitimacy make them uniquely positioned to navigate complex transition environments.
 - *Diaspora philanthropy:* Diaspora giving is more than just charity.⁴⁴ When understood as a long-term investment, it becomes a tool for addressing the root causes of fragility. “The 6T’s of philanthropy” – talent, testimony, ties, time, treasure, and truth – offer a helpful lens for deepening and diversifying the diaspora’s philanthropic contributions.⁴⁵
 - *Diaspora investment:* Beyond remittances, diaspora capital can be channelled into entrepreneurship, social enterprise, and infrastructure development. As seen in The Gambia, Lebanon and Zimbabwe, financial and non-financial contributions can shape economic recovery and institutional reform.
5. **Bridge Domestic and Foreign Policy:** Diaspora capital – economic, human, social, and cultural – can support reforms of national institutions, expand civic space, and unlock development financing. When diasporas are included in both domestic and international policy frameworks, engagement is more likely to be coherent, credible, and impactful. Equally, linking diaspora engagement to shared domestic goals enhances local ownership.

Conclusion

In an era of compounding crises and shrinking aid, diaspora engagement offers one of the most underutilised yet powerful levers for advancing successful transitions. Diaspora communities bring not only remittances, but also technical expertise, global influence, and deep-rooted commitment to the places they come from. Their contributions span the full spectrum of diaspora capital – economic, human, social, and cultural – and their hybrid identities position them uniquely to bridge local realities and international systems.

Realising the full potential of diasporas entails more than symbolic outreach. It requires structured partnerships, shared leadership, and policies that treat diaspora actors not as passive contributors but as co-architects of transitions. When integrated intentionally and inclusively, diaspora engagement can help ensure that transitions are not only locally grounded but also more resilient and sustainable.

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